

Sequential data fusion techniques for the authentication of the P.G.I. Senise (“Crusco”) pepper bell

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Bell pepper is the common name of the berry obtained from some varieties of the *Capsicum annuum* species. This agro-food is appreciated all over the world and represents one of the key ingredients in several traditional dishes. Specific varieties of sweet pepper present organoleptic peculiarities, and they have been awarded quality marks as confirmation of their unicity (e.g., Piment d’Espelette, Pimiento de Herbón, Peperone di Senise). Due to the market value of this aliment and its widespread use as a seasoning (dried and ground), it can easily be subjected to fraud, such as adulteration and sophistication with similar products, i.e. paprika. The proposed adulteration-detection study lays on these considerations, and it aims at developing a non-destructive approach for authenticating Senise bell pepper and detecting its adulteration with common paprika. In order to achieve this goal, mid- and near-infrared spectroscopies were used to analyze 60 pure samples of bell pepper from Senise and 40 mixtures of Senise bell pepper and paprika to mimic the adulteration. Eventually, two different multi-block classification approaches, sequential and orthogonalized partial least squares (Biancolillo and Næs, 2019)-linear discriminant analysis (SO-PLS-LDA) and sequential and orthogonalized covariance selection-linear discriminant analysis (SO-CovSel-PLS-LDA), were used to discriminate between pure and adulterated Senise bell pepper samples. Both proposed procedures were compared with classification models, using the strategy based on the fusion of different pre-treatments through SO-PLS-LDA called sequential preprocessing through orthogonalization (SPORT) (Roger et al., 2020), built on each spectroscopic block individually. SPORT models achieved good accuracies with correct classification rates of 93.3 and 86.7% using MIR and NIR data, respectively; whereas both multi-block approaches reached extremely successful results in external validation, correctly classifying all the (thirty-five) test samples, confirming that better performances are expected when multi-block methodologies are preferred to the disjoint analysis of the individual data blocks.

Keywords: bell pepper, data fusion, authentication, NIR, SO-PLS, SO-CovSel

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